

Learn about the Ayurvedic Treatment for Thyroid Abnormalities in less than 5 minutes

Thyroid disorders affect around 1 million Australians, according to the Australian Thyroid Association. Thyroid disease may be caused by overproduction or underproduction of thyroid hormones. Medication to rectify the hormonal imbalance is typically the basic therapy for thyroid issues. However, many individuals want to know whether [Ayurvedic Treatment for Thyroid Abnormalities](#) might help them manage their symptoms.

Ayurvedic medicine may help you manage your thyroid condition in addition to current therapies, but it should not be used in lieu of them.

In this post, we'll look at Ayurvedic medicine and what science indicates about its usefulness in treating thyroid diseases.

What is Ayurvedic Medicine?

Ayurvedic medicine is one of the world's most ancient traditional medical systems. It dates back over 3,000 years in India and tries to prevent sickness by balancing the mind, soul, and body. It is now a frequently used kind of complementary medicine.

According to Ayurveda, the cosmos is made up of five elements:

- fire
- air
- space
- earth
- water

The three humours of the human body, vata, pitta, and kapha, are made up of these five components. When these three doshas fall out of balance, illnesses are said to arise.

To prevent illness, Ayurvedic medicine employs a comprehensive approach that includes exercise, dietary adjustments, and lifestyle changes. Many Ayurvedic medicines and unprocessed foods might be beneficial additions to your diet. Thyroid problems may be treated with some of these foods.

Ayurvedic Treatment of Hashimoto's Thyroiditis

There is no proof that any Ayurvedic treatment may cure Hashimoto's thyroiditis.

Hashimoto's thyroiditis is an autoimmune condition in which the body attacks the thyroid gland. Hypothyroidism is a frequent result.

Whole foods, such as fruits and vegetables, are recommended by Ayurveda. A nutritious diet will help you maintain your overall health and avoid vitamin shortages, which can lead to further health problems.

Consuming highly processed foods may raise your chance of getting autoimmune illnesses, according to some studies, but more research is required before the relationship can be established.

Ayurvedic Treatment for Hypothyroidism

The adaptogen herb ashwagandha (*Withania somnifera*) aids with stress management. Northern Africa and India are the only places where it grows natively. It is one of Ayurveda's most important herbs.

According to a few small trials, it seems to help cure hypothyroidism by reducing stress hormone levels. More study is required, however, to determine its effectiveness.

Researchers looked at the effects of Ashwagandha on 50 people with moderate hypothyroidism who hadn't progressed to clinical levels in a double-blind, placebo-controlled trial. The subjects were given 600 mg of Ashwagandha root every day for eight weeks by the researchers.

Participants who took Ashwagandha had considerably lower thyroid hormone levels than those who received a placebo at the conclusion of the trial.

In 2014 research, Ashwagandha's influence on thyroid hormone levels in people with bipolar illness was studied. Patients who took Ashwagandha for eight weeks had substantial changes in thyroid hormone levels when compared to those who received a placebo.

Because of the study's shortcomings, the researchers determined that additional research is required.

Ayurvedic Treatment for Hyperthyroidism

There's just a small amount of evidence that Ayurvedic treatment may help with hyperthyroidism symptoms. *Convolvulus pluricaulis* Choisy is a plant that may help with hyperthyroidism (*C. pluricaulis*).

In Indian and Chinese medicine, *C. pluricaulis* is often used to treat a range of ailments, including persistent cough, anxiety, and epilepsy.

An analysis of rat research from 2001 supports the claim that *C. pluricaulis* may cure hyperthyroidism. Thyroid hormones were raised in mice by giving them medicine for a month. The rats' thyroid hormone levels were then measured after the mice were given *C. pluricaulis* extracts.

Thyroid hormone levels, as well as the enzymes hepatic 5'-monodeiodinase and glucose-6-phosphatase, were shown to be reduced by *C. pluricaulis* extract, according to the researchers. Improvements in hyperthyroidism are likely to have been caused by inhibition of hepatic 5'-monodeiodinase.

Further research on humans is needed to find out whether this herb may help people with hyperthyroidism.